

Synthesis of 5-Chloro-1,3-disubstituted Benzimidazolin-2-thiones as Antiinflammatory Agents*

RAJENDRA S. VARMA and DEVESH CHATTERJEE

Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 007

Manuscript received 12 April 1983, revised 16 September 1983, accepted 27 October 1983

A series of 5-chloro-1,3-disubstituted benzimidazolin-2-thiones have been synthesised. The synthesised compounds have been evaluated for their antiinflammatory activity. Mass spectral fragmentation pattern of a few compounds has indicated that these compounds undergo McLafferty rearrangement with charge residing on both the fragments.

ANTIINFLAMMATORY activity¹⁻⁵ and other biological activities⁶⁻⁸ such as antibacterial, antiviral and anthelmintic, exhibited by benzimidazoles, benzothiazoles, benzoxazoles and other closely related heterocyclic systems led us to synthesise a series

of 5-chloro-1,3-disubstituted benzimidazolin-2-thiones for evaluation as antiinflammatory agents.

For the synthesis of 5-chlorobenzimidazolin-2-thione, 4-chloro-*o*-phenylenediamine and CS₂ were heated together in presence of ethanolic KOH. 4-Chloro-*o*-phenylenediamine has been prepared via a number of steps starting from 4-chloroaniline as shown in the Chart 1.

For the synthesis of the title compounds (III-V), 5-chlorobenzimidazolin-2-thione was treated with 40% aqueous formaldehyde solution. II thus obtained was condensed with various amines to furnish the title compounds. They were also obtained directly from 5-chlorobenzimidazolin-2-thione under the condition of Mannich reaction. 5-Chlorobenzimidazolin-2-thione on acetylation yielded VI. All the synthesised compounds were characterised by correct elemental analysis and spectral data.

The nmr spectrum of IIIe (R = CO₂Et) is in accordance with the assigned structure. Signals (chemical shift in δ scale) were observed at 1.20 (t, -CH₃), 4.06 (q, -O-CH₂-), 5.70 (d, N-CH₂-N), 6.43-7.83 (Ar-H and NH protons).

In the mass spectrum of III (R = H) (Chart 2), the molecular ion undergoes McLafferty rearrangement exhibiting characteristic peaks at *m/e* 184/186 (1) and *m/e* 105 (2). Loss of aniline, [*m/e* 93 (3)] from the molecular ion via an intermediate ion 'A' is also an important fragmentation process. The ion 2 then ejects a hydrogen radical followed by loss of HCN leading to ions at *m/e* 104 (4) and *m/e* 77. The ion 1 could lose a Cl radical yielding ion at *m/e* 149. Alternatively, successive removal of a sulphur atom and HCN could lead to ions 6 (*m/e* 152/154) and at *m/e* 125/127.

Biological activity :

Five compounds of the series were evaluated for antiinflammatory activity and acute toxicity.

Chart 1

* Part XLII of the series "Potential Biologically Active Agents".

Chart 2

Acute toxicity :

LD₅₀ values of compounds were determined in albino mice obtained from the colony bred at CDRI,

Lucknow. Four mice were taken in one group for the study and a group of four mice served as control. Graded doses of the compounds were given to the test animals intraperitoneally using 2% gum acacia solution as vehicle. Controls were given gum acacia solution only. The effects were observed for 3 hr after administration and the mortality was noted after 24 hr. The LD₅₀ and the confidence limits were evaluated by the method of Horn⁹. The data are given in Table 1.

Antiinflammatory activity :

Antiinflammatory activity was evaluated in mice by carrageenin induced oedema method at 1/5 of the LD₅₀ as described by Winter *et al*¹⁰ for rats. A group of 5 mice was used and the compound was administered orally 1 hr before the injection of the phlogistic agent. Oedema was induced by injecting 0.025 ml freshly prepared suspension of carrageenin (1% in normal saline) in the subplanter region of the left paw, the other paw acting as control. The animals were killed with ether 4 hr later and both the limbs were cut identically at the lower end of tibia. The difference in the weights of treated and untreated paws was a measure of the suppressive action of the compound tested¹¹. The inhibitory activities are expressed as percentage inhibition and the results are included in Table 1. Out of the 5 compounds tested, 4 exhibited significant antiinflammatory activity. Compounds IIIg and VI exhibited maximum inhibition of 35 and 38%, respectively.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes in sulfuric acid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer 177 spectrophotometer and nmr on Varian A-60D instrument

TABLE 1—5-CHLORO-1,8-DISUBSTITUTED BENZIMIDAZOLIN-2-THIONES (III-VI)

Comp. No.	R	Yield %	m.p. °C	mol. formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			LD ₅₀ mg/kg i.p.	C.L.* mg/kg	% inhibition
					O	H	N			
IIIa	H	61	146-47	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ClN ₂ S	68.80 (63.87)	4.30 (4.81)		1000	Nil	7.8
IIIb	Cl	42	153-55	C ₁₁ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₂ S	54.00 (54.36)	4.18 (3.66)	11.69 (12.08)			
IIIc	-OCH ₃	66	113-15	C ₁₂ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₂ S 1/2 H ₂ O	60.25 (59.54)	5.15 (5.17)				
III d	-COOH	41	220-22	C ₁₂ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₄ S	56.70 (57.20)	4.38 (3.99)		464	298-723	22.1
III e	COOC ₂ H ₅	56	183-90	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₄ S	60.90 (60.16)	5.66 (5.01)				
III f	COOCH ₃	52	130-35 ^d	C ₁₂ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₄ S 1 1/2 H ₂ O	55.95 (55.81)	4.48 (4.88)				
III g	CH ₂ COOH	60	150-55 ^d	C ₁₃ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₄ S H ₂ O	57.20 (56.76)	5.14 (4.73)		681	396-1170	35
IV	—	53	203-05	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₄ S H ₂ O	51.40 (50.93)	5.85 (6.24)		316	Nil	33
V	—	57	110-12	C ₁₀ H ₉ ClN ₂ S			14.75 (14.79)			
VI	—	66	196-98	C ₁₁ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₂ S			10.07 (10.42)	316	Nil	38

Compound No. IIIb and IIIc were prepared by method B only. All compounds were recrystallised from methanol except compound No. VI which was crystallised from chloroform.

* C.L. = Confidence limit.

in CDCl_3 using TMS as an internal reference. Mass spectra were recorded at 70 eV on a Hitachi RMU-6E instrument.

5-Chlorobenzimidazolin-2-thione (I) : A mixture of 4-chloro-*o*-phenylenediamine (4.3 g; 0.03 mole) prepared via a number of steps as shown in Chart 1, KOH (1.9 g) and CS_2 (2.6 g; 0.03 mole) in 95% ethanol (30 ml) and water (5 ml) was heated under reflux for 3 hr. Norit was added to it cautiously and after refluxing for 10 min it was filtered hot. The hot filtrate was diluted with 30 ml warm water and a solution of 2.4 ml acetic acid in 5 ml water was added to it with brisk stirring. The product separated as white lumps. The mixture was refrigerated overnight and filtered. It was crystallised from methanol-water, m.p. 302° (lit. 294° ¹²), yield 50%.

5-Chloro-1,3-dihydroxymethylbenzimidazolin-2-thione (II) : I (1.8 g; 0.01 mole) was dissolved in a minimum amount of ethanol and 4 ml of formalin (40%) was added to it. The reaction mixture was warmed on a water bath. The product separated on cooling, which was filtered, washed with cold ethanol and dried, m.p. $175-77^\circ$, yield 83%.

II being unstable could not be purified for elemental analysis. In order to establish its structure, II was refluxed with acetic anhydride for 0.5 hr and the mixture was poured upon cracked ice. The acetyl derivative (IIa) thus obtained was crystallised from methanol, m.p. $141-42^\circ$, yield 60%. (Found : C, 47.80; H, 3.98. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$ requires C, 47.48; H, 3.95%). IR (KBr) in cm^{-1} : 1750 (C=O). NMR (CDCl_3 , δ) : 2.03 (s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 6.2 (s, N- CH_2 -O), 7.2 (d, 6 and 7 aromatic protons), 7.35 (s, 4 aromatic proton).

5-Chloro-1,3-diaminomethylbenzimidazolin-2-thiones (III-V) :

Method (A) : I (1.8 g; 0.01 mole), dissolved in minimum amount of methanol, was treated with 2 ml formalin (40%) and an appropriate amine (0.02 mole) with brisk stirring. The mixture was further stirred for 15 min at room temp and left overnight. The product separated was filtered and recrystallised repeatedly to analytical purity from methanol.

Method (B) : II (1.2 g; 0.005 mole) and a suitable amine (0.01 mole) were refluxed for 1 hr in 10 ml ethanol. The contents were kept in a deep freeze overnight and the solid thus obtained was filtered, washed with cold methanol and recrystallised.

IR (KBr) in cm^{-1} :

IIIa, 3375 (NH); IIIb, 3450 (NH), 1100 (C-Cl); IIIc, 3325 (NH), 1240, 1040 (C-O-C); IIId, 3350 (NH), 1665 (C=O), 2700-3200 (O-H); IIIe

3325 (NH), 1675 (C=O), 1260 (C-C=O); IIIf, 3350

(NH), 1690 (C=O), 1260 (C-C=O); IIIg, 3350 (NH), 1660 (C=O), 2800-3250 (O-H); IV, 2825 (CH_2); V, 2830 (CH_2).

NMR (CDCl_3 , δ) : IIIe, 1.20 (t, $-\text{CH}_3$), 4.06 (q, O- CH_2 -), 5.70 (d, N- CH_2 -N), 6.43-7.83 (Ar-H and N-H). Mass : IIIa, 184/186, 152/154, 149, 125/127, 105, 104, 93, 92, 66, 65. IIIb, 184/186, 139/141, 138/140, 127/129, 111/113.

5-Chloro-1,3-diacetylbenzimidazolin-2-thione (VI) : I (0.9 g; 0.005 mole) and acetic anhydride (3 ml) were refluxed for 1 hr and then the reaction mixture was poured into cold water. The solid thus obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallised from chloroform, m.p. 203° , yield 66%. IR (KBr) in cm^{-1} : 1720 (C=O). (Found : N, 10.07. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires 10.42%).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Head of the Chemistry Department, Lucknow University for facilities and Dr. R. S. Kapil of C.D.R.I., Lucknow for analytical/spectral data and Dr. R. C. Srimal and Dr. C. R. Prasad of C.D.R.I., Lucknow for biological activity tests. One of the authors (D.C.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

- G. TSUKAMOTO, K. YOSHINO, T. KOHNO, H. OHTAKA, H. KAGAYA and K. ITO, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1980, **23**, 734.
- T. NOSE, T. KOHNO, K. YOSHINO, K. ITO, H. KAGAYA and G. TSUKAMOTO, *Japan Kokai Tokkyo Koho*, 7995734, 1979; *Chem. Abs.*, 1980, **92**, 82480b.
- T. TAKASHIMA, Y. KADOH and S. KUMADA, *Arznei. Forsch.*, 1972, **22**, 711.
- T. OKADA, K. NAITO, T. KIKUCHI and T. SANO, *Japan Kokai Tokkyo Koho*, 7998787, 1979; *Chem. Abs.*, 1980, **92**, 588824n.
- S. INOUE, K. OHATA, T. TSUTSUI, M. TANIGUCHI and M. KOBAYASHI, *Japan Kokai Tokkyo Koho*, 7930161, 1979; *Chem. Abs.*, 1980, **91**, 56988z.
- A. LESPAGNOL, J. MERCIA and C. LESPAGNOL, *Arch. Intern. Pharmacodyn.*, 1953, **94**, 212.
- R. S. VARMA and W. L. NOBLE, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1968, **57**, 39.
- N. D. MIKHNOVSKA and O. V. STETSSENCO, *Mikrobiol. Zh.*, 1967, **29**, 242; *Chem. Abs.*, 1967, **67**, 97905.
- H. J. HORN, *Biometrics*, 1956, **12**, 311.
- C. A. WINTER, E. A. RISLILY and G. W. NUSS, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1962, **111**, 544.
- R. C. SRIMAL and B. N. DHAWAN, *Indian J. Pharmac.* 1971, **3**, 4.
- O. FISCHER and F. LIMMER, *J. Prak. Chem.*, 1906, **74**, 60.